

Some Reactions of *p*-Nitrobenzal-*o*-methoxy-*p*-bromoacetophenone

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Benzalacetophenone derivative (1) was allowed to react with hydrazines, hydroxylaminehydrochloride, thiourea and bromine to give Δ^2 -pyrazolines (2a,b), Δ^2 -isoxazoline (3), tetrahydropyrimidinethione derivative (4) and the chalcone dibromide (5) respectively. Compound 4 was reacted with hydrazinehydrate, acid hydrazides, phenylisocyanate and secondary amines (under Mannich reaction conditions) to give hydrazinopyrimidine (6), triazolopyrimidines (7,8), pyrimidinethione (9) and Mannich bases (10a-c) respectively. Compound 5 when reacted with hydroxylamine hydrochloride and hydrazines gave 3 and 2a,b respectively.

As an extension of our studies on α,β -unsaturated carbonyl compounds¹, treatment of α,β -unsaturated ketones with hydrazines and hydroxylaminehydrochloride gave pyrazolines and isoxazolines respectively^{2,3}. The tetrahydropyrimidinethione derivative of benzalacetophenone has been prepared⁴. It is reported that bromination of chalcone in carbon tetrachloride afforded the corresponding dibromide⁵, and the chalcone dibromide gave pyrazolines and isoxazolines on treatment with hydrazines and hydroxylamine hydrochloride respectively⁶. Literature^{7,8} also describes the synthesis and biological evaluation of the product of the reaction of pyrimidinethione towards hydrazines, acid hydrazides, phenylisocyanate and secondary amines under condition of Mannich reaction.

Results and Discussion

The reaction of 1 with hydrazine hydrate or phenylhydrazine in ethanol, yielded the hydrazones which rearranged immediately to the pyrazoline derivatives (2a,b) (Scheme 1).

Treatment of 1 with hydroxylamine hydrochloride in boiling ethanol gave the isoxazoline derivative (3). The reaction of 1 with thiourea in boiling ethanol yielded the tetrahydropyrimidinethione derivative (4). Treatment of 1 with bromine in carbon tetrachloride or acetic acid yielded the corresponding dibromide (5).

Scheme 1

Compound 4 was reacted with hydrazine-hydrate in boiling ethanol to afford the hydrazinopyrimidine derivative (6) which showed activity in tests predicative of anxiolytic activity^{7,9} (Scheme 2). Treatment of 6 with boiling acetic acid gave the triazolopyrimidine derivative (7) whose structure was proved via its unambiguous synthesis by in-

teraction of the pyrimidinethione (4) with acetylhydrazine in refluxing butanol and also by analytical and spectral data. Similarly 4 reacted with *p*-

Scheme 2

chlorobenzoylhydrazine to give 8. Interestingly compound 4 reacted with phenylisocyanate in boiling benzene to form the pyrimidinethione derivative (9) (Scheme 2).

Amines and aqueous formaldehyde in boiling ethanol reacted with compound 4 to yield the Mannich bases (10a-c) which were reported as potential biological agents, as dyes and surface active compounds⁹. On the other hand, the chalcone dibromide (5) was reacted with hydrazines in boiling acetic acid to give the pyrazoline derivatives (2a,b). Also, 5 was condensed with hydroxylamine hydrochloride in boiling acetic acid to yield Δ^2 -isoxazoline derivative (3).

Experimental

All m.p.s. are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr) were run on a Unicam Sp-200G spectrophotometer, mass spectra on a Varian MAT 711 spectrometer (70 eV) and nmr spectra (CDCl_3) on a Varian A60 spectrometer using TMS as an internal standard.

Δ^2 -Pyrazoline (2a,b) : A mixture of 1 and/or 5 (0.01 mol) and hydrazine hydrate and/or phenylhydrazine (0.015 mol) in ethanol or acetic acid (30 ml) was refluxed for 7 h. The resulting solid after cooling was crystallised from methanol to yield the pyrazolines: 2a, m.p. 165–67° (Found: C, 49.71; H, 3.54; N, 10.69. $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{14}\text{BrN}_3\text{O}_3$ calcd. for : C, 49.74; H, 3.62; N, 10.88%); ν_{max} 1616–1450 (C=N), 3300 cm^{-1} (NH); 2b, m.p. 178° (Found : C, 57.14; H, 3.89; N, 9.09 $\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{18}\text{BrN}_3\text{O}_3$ calcd for : C, 57.14; H, 3.89, N, 9.09%); ν_{max} 1616–1450 (C=N), 1630 cm^{-1} .

Δ^2 -Isoxazoline (3) : A mixture of 1 and/or 5 (0.01 mol) and hydroxylamine hydrochloride (0.02 mol) in ethanol or acetic acid (30 ml) was refluxed for 8 h. The reaction mixture was cooled and poured in ice-cold water. The resulting solid was crystallised from methanol to yield the product, m.p. 160° (Found : C, 49.48; H, 3.28, N, 7.09. $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{11}\text{BrN}_2\text{O}_4$ calcd. for : C, 49.16; H, 3.35; N, 7.23%); ν_{max} 1640 cm^{-1} (C=N); m/z M^+ 387.

Tetrahydropyrimidinethione derivative (4) : A mixture of 1 (0.01 mol), thiourea (0.01 mol) and KOH (1 g in 30 ml absolute ethanol) was refluxed for 7 h. On concentration and cooling the separated solid was crystallised from methanol, m.p. 205° (Found : C, 47.44; H, 3.25; N, 9.76; S, 7.44. $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{14}\text{BrN}_3\text{O}_3\text{S}$ calcd. for : C, 46.90; H, 3.09; N, 9.67; S, 7.09%); ν_{max} 1395–1440 (C=S), 3270–3300 cm^{-1} (NH); m/z M^+ 430.

Chalcone dibromide (5) : A stirred solution of 1 (0.01 mol) in carbon tetrachloride or acetic acid (30 ml) was treated with bromine (0.01 mol) in the same solvent (20 ml). The mixture was left overnight and the solvent evaporated under reduced pressure to give a reddish solid

which was crystallised from benzene, m.p. 98° (Found : C, 34.78; H, 2.17; N, 2.53. C₁₆H₁₂Br₃NO₄; calcd. for : C, 33.92; H, 2.06; N, 2.30%); ν_{\max} 1700 cm⁻¹ (C=O); δ 3.8 (3H, s, OCH₃), 4.8–5.2 (2H, d, CH), 8.3 (7H, m, ArH).

Hydrazinopyrimidine derivative (6) : A mixture of **4** (0.01 mol) and hydrazine hydrate (0.01 mol) in absolute ethanol (20 ml) was refluxed for 6 h. The reaction mixture was then cooled and the resulting solid was crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 148° (Found : C, 47.66; H, 3.73; N, 16.35. C₁₇H₁₆BrN₅O₃ calcd. for : C, 47.11; H, 3.61; N, 16.55%).

Triazolopyrimidine derivative (7). Method A : A mixture of compound **6** (0.01 mol) and hydrazine hydrate (0.01 mol) was refluxed in acetic acid (20 ml) for 6 h. The reaction mixture was then cooled and the resulting solid was crystallised from methanol, m.p. 228° (Found : C, 50.44; H, 3.53; N, 15.48. C₁₉H₁₆BrN₅O₃ calcd. for : C, 49.29; H, 3.17; N, 15.20%); ν_{\max} 1600–1640 cm⁻¹ (C=N); δ 3.1 (2H, d, CH₂ cyclic), 2.7 (3H, s, CH₃), 3.8 (3H, s, OCH₃), 4.2 (1H, d, N-CH) and 6.9–8.2 (7H, m, ArH).

Method B : A mixture of **4** (0.01 mol) and acetylhydrazine (0.01 mol) in absolute ethanol (25 ml) was refluxed for 8 h. The reaction mixture was then cooled and the resulting solid was crystallised from methanol to yield the product.

Triazolopyrimidine derivative (8) : A mixture of **4** (0.01 mol) and *p*-chlorobenzoylhydrazine (0.01 mol) in ethanol (30 ml) was refluxed for 8 h. The solid obtained after cooling was crystallised from methanol, m.p. 246° (Found : C, 52.50; H, 3.09; N, 12.76. C₂₄H₁₇BrClN₅O₃ calcd. for : C, 51.84; H, 2.88; N, 12.39%).

Pyrimidinethione derivative (9) : A mixture of **4** (0.01 mol) and phenylisocyanate (0.01 mol) in dry benzene (20 ml) was refluxed for 1 h. The reaction mixture was then cooled, and the

resulting solid was crystallised from benzene, m.p. 183° (Found : C, 52.55; H, 3.46; N, 10.20; S, 5.82. C₂₄H₁₉BrN₄SO₄ calcd. for : C, 52.03; H, 2.98; N, 10.01; S, 5.61%); ν_{\max} 1650–1665 (C=O of carboxamide) and 3250–3300 cm⁻¹ (NH).

Mannich bases (10a-c) : A mixture of **4** (0.01 mol), formaldehyde (0.01 mol) and secondary amine (namely, diethylamine, piperidine and/or morpholine) (0.01 mol) in ethanol (30 ml) was refluxed for 4 h. The reaction mixture was then concentrated and cooled. The resulting solid was crystallised from ethanol to yield the products : **10a**, m.p. 206° (Found : C, 47.86; H, 4.71; N, 10.15; S, 5.80. C₂₂H₂₆BrClN₄SO₃ calcd. for : C, 47.29; H, 4.56; N, 9.87; S, 5.71%); **10b**, m.p. 173° (Found : C, 46.76; H, 4.07; N, 9.92; S, 5.66. C₂₂H₂₃BrClN₄SO₄ calcd. for : C, 45.83; H, 3.72; N, 9.81; S, 5.38%); **10c**, m.p. 197° (Found : C, 49.06; H, 4.44; N, 9.59; S, 5.68. C₂₃H₂₅BrClN₄SO₃ calcd. for : C, 48.69; H, 4.38; N, 9.12; S, 5.54%); ν_{\max} 1440–1410 (C=S) and 3300–3200 cm⁻¹ (NH).

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